

THE MOON'S DUNGEON CITY. A FUTURISTIC ARCHITECTURAL MODEL OF THE UNDERGROUND LUNAR STATION

Abstract

The article discusses the idea of a moon city. Its main principles are defined as: fractality, modularity, connectivity, multifunctionality, and scalability. The fractality is based on a copy-paste system. The modularity enables the creation of continuously evolving architectural forms. The connectivity allows you to mix everything. The multifunctionality makes it possible to create a hybrid urban context. The scalability may adjust, expand, or reduce the city. Based on the identified principles, the authors demonstrate how the Moon becomes a platform for the implementation of completely new architectural ideas. A basic concept involves placing the city beneath the lunar surface. The Moon's Dungeon City is an underground multi-level megastructure. It gradually reshapes the celestial body, eventually becoming its duplicate. The city can evolve, potentially developing into a self-sustaining, planetary-scale ecosystem.

Key words:

Lunar station, moon city, architecture of the future, megastructure, lunar dungeon, underground city, fractal, hyperobject.

Introduction

Modern reality has led humanity into an era of implementing bold ideas in outer space. Developing efficient architectural solutions is one of the key tasks today. However, common design principles become irrelevant within the context of the cosmos.

For example, a physical body in space is constantly in motion due to gravity. This forces us to rethink the concept of a visuality and also the architecture as a spatial complex. In other words, a space object is not perceived in one fixed configuration. Its form is transforming and moving, thus creating multiple viewpoints. Therefore, an object in space is a 360-degree panorama that continually alters with the displacement of the spacecraft and celestial bodies. Moreover, in complete darkness and without visual landmarks, the concept of movement becomes abstract.

It is crucial to develop new approaches for working with architecture in space or on another planet. In the near future, Earth's satellite is a good research area for forming new principles of space architecture. The authors aimed to develop architectural methods for designing a settlement on the Moon. The lunar conditions will not only create an image of new architecture but also act as a trigger for the development of fundamentally different spatial forms, styles, and theories.

Relevance of research

To establish a settlement on the Moon, humanity needs to abandon the conventional architectural vision within the "Human-Earth" system to declare a new "Human-Universe" paradigm [2].

The lunar landscape has distinctive features. There is no atmosphere, which leads to sharp temperature fluctuations between day and night and, as a result, weak protection from solar radiation and micrometeorites. Consequently, the base must be strategically located in a secure area. Craters or lava caves could become shelters and integrated structural elements of the settlement. Lunar regolith, with its sharp particles, poses a significant hazard when airborne. Therefore, it is necessary to create a mobile automated infrastructure, detached from the lunar surface to minimize any contact with

the ground. The monotonous landscape makes traditional orientation impossible on the Moon. And the absence of a sound environment requires the architect to focus on developing visually striking architecture, as well as creating an advanced spatial system. In other words, it is necessary to create a complex visual-spatial landscape that functions as an architectural compass to determine location and next route.

The Moon presents an opportunity for architectural innovation that may never be possible on Earth. The unique environment poses a challenge for architects to explore groundbreaking and experimental solutions.

The authors propose three types of space architecture:

- flexible architecture;
- mobile architecture;
- multivariate architecture.

Flexible architecture

Considering the feasibility of using inflatable modules as a convenient way of forming quick-build residential units, it can be assumed that liquid and soft lunar shapes will replace the rigid and linear forms typical of terrestrial architecture. This flexible architecture will be able to adapt to extreme conditions on the Moon, expanding and shrinking as needed. Moreover, this type of stretch fabric can unlock the potential of the complex multi-layered lunar landscape that includes plains, crevasses, mountains, craters and lava caves. The architectural structure is capable of filling gaps or creating spaces for novel architectural configurations. The similarities of flexible architecture can also be found in astronaut costumes. This idea originated in Archigram's architectural utopias of the 20th century. Architecture pressed to the body can take any form, it only needs to be inflated. For example, a "second skin" can accommodate other crew members and be extended into a small settlement [16]. This outfit is multi-size. It can be

inhabited and propagate life. Mixing people, sounds, smells and functions, this sensory cloud can fill the Moon. In other words, flexible architecture may activate any scenario for lunar urban development.

Mobile architecture

The initial phase of lunar space exploration will set the trajectory for the development of mobile architecture. The authors propose an autonomous cabin that is delivered to the surface of the Moon and begins to function as an independent architectural module. It is characterized by its ability to transform the surrounding space, providing a new level of freedom. The main element of this is the mechanical communication lines, laid out for the construction of the lunar base. Architectural cabins ride on them and combine to form a modular settlement. In addition, the communication lines should be able to intersect, providing a variety of routes. This design ensures that the lunar base can continue to function fully even if one of the habitable cells is damaged by meteorite impacts or a technical accident. The structure leaves the broken element until it is repaired and works in an alternative way. Thus, the mobile architecture performs a "self-regenerative" function. Finally, the highways of the lunar settlement can be connected to the outer landscape. After being disassembled and reconstructed in a new location, the moon city has the ability to relocate. Its dynamic structure is capable of rapid spatial growth and reproduction. Theoretically, a lunar city can take over all the space on the Moon.

Multivariate architecture

The possibility of combining modules and various architectural systems used in space missions enables the concept of multivariate architecture. An architect can constantly change configurations, adapting to new needs and circumstances. This potential for ongoing transformation

represents a fundamental shift in lunar city design. The urban system's infinite growth and combinations make this multivariate landscape unique. Taking the idea to its limit, we could contemplate creating an architecture for the planet. In ancient Greece, the term "Megalopolis" or "city of cities" described a city-state. Today, a new phenomenon has emerged called "Planet City". Liam Young used the term to describe his visionary project. Planet City is a radical, provocative idea that visually examines extreme urban densification as a potential reversal to climate catastrophe [17]. According to this view, the city becomes an architectural megastructure [1]. New ideas for a sustainable future are opened up by the concept of the planet as an "architectural designer". The planet's computer and quantum capabilities can be utilized to solve complex environmental problems. We need models that are liquid, intuitive, and conscious, not mathematical and logical formulas. Moving from units and objects to flows, fields, tissues, and membranes is necessary. The master plan of the planet is limited to a geometric grid, leaving behind its details. It works as a graphic, compositional and artistic palette. The drawing becomes alive and begins to change. This philosophy requires architects to consider structures, matrices, megaplans, networks and platforms [11]. The planetary city is attracting a new type of urban dwellers. The authors consider it to be a metahuman: someone who is completely integrated into infinite space and can be in all its places simultaneously. Quantum geometry is the inspiration for multivariate architecture, which allows us to view the city as a field for architectural experiments.

The conclusion is that radically different and extreme design conditions are not an obstacle, but rather the formation of new dogmas that extend architectural boundaries to a planetary scale.

Concept

The authors emphasize important positions that could play a crucial role in developing innovative architectural and spatial solutions for a lunar city:

- Meteor showers hit the Moon. We need to make a sheltered architecture. To minimize risks, a complex underground urban system is proposed. Craters, lava caves, holes, and the anthropogenic level are all elements of a subterranean landscape. Robert Anson Heinlein's science fiction novel "The Moon is a Harsh Mistress" resembles this approach [7]. The story is about underground tunnels used to protect against the Moon's aggressive environment, which subsequently led to the discovery of lunar ice. In other words, the Moon's dungeon is an ideal location for building the city. The temperature remains at 17 degrees Celsius in the underground layer, while it fluctuates between plus 130 and minus 173 on the surface. As a consequence, the comfortable belowground environment enables more innovative architecture [13]. For instance, a base situated inside a tunnel must have a rigid structure and consist of integral blocks. Dynamic modules form the beginning and end of the structure, while static ones comprise the middle. The former are responsible for adaptation, while the latter maintain the system. The city has an entry and exit. And the visitor must finish the script. The adventure starts at the surface and descends into the depths, reminiscent of the Dungeons of the Underdark. Heroes are surface folk boldly venturing into the uncharted Centre of the Moon. The map of the city is illustrated in Figure 1;

Figure 1: The Moon's Dungeon. Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.

- The moon has no atmosphere. While air is an important resource for humans. This necessitates the creation of enclosed and protected spaces [3]. As a result, autonomous modular structures of residential units with overlapping lines have been developed. The disassembly of lines creates a space gap. It can be used to transform the base, when necessary. This structural design allows for the separation of a non-functioning module from the base and creates a new branch of development. The city is formed within the vector interface that consists of nodes, loops and branches. The architect can manage their settings and set city parameters. The spatial development of this enclosed horizontal city is only possible through the integration and multiplication of volumes. This points out the importance of creating visual, tactile, and sound designs for the interior space. In the absence of a natural environment, it is capable of maintaining the crew's psycho-emotional well-being. Therefore, we must create an inner multi-level system that can replace the exterior landscape both visually and functionally. The principle is illustrated in Figure 2;

Figure 2: Principle of branching tunnels with overlapping communication systems. Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.

- The space shuttle plays a pivotal role in lunar architecture. It delivers the original buildings to the Moon. In other words, a lunar city consists of modules, which are limited by the physical parameters of the spacecraft's fuselage [15]. Our task is to create an extended combination of the base, using a limited number of the spatial element constructor. Consequently, the lunar city has initial units with an endless variety of connectivity. By choosing a strategy, the architect can influence the city's appearance. For example, you can create an initially widely developed city by spending all the elements of the constructor. It is a moderate strategy for creating a base. The focus is on wild evolution, colonization of vast areas and long-term autonomous maintenance. As a result, it hibernates the city very soon. Another option is to create small mobile architectural blocks, which move freely on the surface, spread over a small area and utilize parts of the constructor for gradual growth. This enables the city to stay active and adaptable for a long time. In this case, the architect chooses an aggressive and expansive strategy for creating a base. This is illustrated in Figure 3;

Figure 3: The principle of commonality of elements of the spatial system "ship-settlement". Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.

- The integral landscape makes the city free. It may develop in any direction. New urban land may redistribute functional, engineering and technological potential of the Moon. At first, spacecraft will use the integral landscape to drop architectural elements. Its primary function is twofold: to incorporate new resources delivered from above and to remove obsolete or malfunctioning system components from below. This structure serves as an intermediate zone between the inner station and the external environment. Like an ancient, powerful genie, it instantly connects any points in space and finds objects hidden on the other side of the Moon. Moreover, the integral landscape possesses the remarkable ability to transform falling meteorites and cosmic dust into viable building materials. The lunar mission's final stage involves the spacecraft's landing onto this adaptive terrain. So, it can be used as a resource surface for recycling previously used space shuttles. We may turn spacecrafts, rocket ships, satellites and

other robotic machines into elements of the zero cycle. The principle is illustrated in Figure 4;

Figure 4: The city's surface absorbs space debris and generates resources. Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.

- Plug-in architecture may set up a moon city. All its parts are interconnected: "micro-micro", "micro-macro", "macro-micro", "macro-macro". Any element of the city can be removed and implemented. Regardless of their size or function, all parts of the city share a common connectivity system. Elements are involved in dynamic relationships. In other words, a kettle can connect to a building, and a building unites with a mobile kitchen complex. You may puzzle architecture to make a Frankenstein-like monster. The principle is illustrated in Figure 5;

Figure 5: The elements of the system are in a dynamic relationship. Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.

- The uneven surface of the Moon prevents free movement. To solve this problem, we must develop a hybrid architecture, with movement and levitation modular systems [5]. A symbiotic communication network with a well-developed internal infrastructure. By allowing the movement of settlements from one place to another, the potential for shaping architecture is increased. Moreover, the division of the communication network into levels solves multiple problems. Among other things, it will help minimize contact with the lunar surface where hazardous dust particles pose a serious threat. At the top, you can find the automated rail line. Below, there are two strips for both people and moon scooters. The Moon's lack of a sound-conducting atmosphere makes it impossible to rely on audible signals to warn of approaching robotic transport modules. That is why having all communication systems on the same level is

extremely dangerous. Secondly, communication lines can perform an additional service function. All throughout, there are compartments that contain first aid equipment and vehicle repair tools. Thirdly, it is feasible to continue the line up to the spaceport and connect it directly to the landing shuttle. This will help astronauts get from the ship to the base without leaving the interior. Finally, elevated systems above the ground perform a visual function, helping people to navigate. Vertical dominants are well visible from a great distance. The system is illustrated in Figure 6;

Figure 6. Flow diagram of continuous communication internal environment above the ground. Graphic illustration: Irina S. Kozlova.

- Long nights and days make a different time frame. Jimenez Lai, in his project "Spaceship Hour" (2021) reflected on the fact that determining time in outer space conditions will become difficult and, to some extent, meaningless [8]. Timelessness and Darkness. Wake up, Architect! Time has you. To defeat it, you must follow the White Rabbit, as Neo did, and get into a situation similar to the Matrix. On Earth, we can easily orient ourselves in time inside a building by looking out

the window. The window is a clock, and the door serves as a boundary between different time zones (street and house). However, on a lunar base, where the entire infrastructure functions as a symbiotic network, doors only play a role in the formation of zoning. A lifeless space prevents you from looking out. In addition, long lunar nights and days make visual orientation in time impossible. Considering that windows and doors are important elements in design, it becomes quite obvious that developing a lunar facade is futile. This is illustrated in Figure 7;

*Figure 7. Diagram of the street-corridor and building-rooms.
Graphic illustration: Irina S. Kozlova.*

- The Moon's isolation drives human architecture. A person is unable to socialize for extended periods during a journey. This can result in cognitive and emotional impairments that could jeopardize the mission. Therefore, it is crucial to propose an architectural solution that prioritizes human needs in space [9]. We must create an environment that facilitates smooth interaction among crew members. Through the mobility

of each living unit, it is possible to create a communication network within the base to maintain social interaction [6]. Residents have the flexibility to integrate their living units and join new communities or, conversely, disconnect and enjoy periods of solitude. To take a balance is the first aim. The communication system is illustrated in Figure 8;

*Figure 8. Diagram of unified communication network of base.
Graphic illustration: Irina S. Kozlova.*

- A uniform landscape makes navigation impossible. If a person moves away from the base and neglects topographical landmarks, he will likely become disoriented. Therefore, the architect is required to create a complex space that illuminates the lunar base and acts as a landmark. To achieve this solution, it is possible to utilize striking geometry and incorporate all city-building elements into a single architectural complex. As an example, a complex can have beacons that function as both visual compass and pit stop. Firstly, it may project a message to any location. By doing this, the crew can be informed of an emergency. Secondly, a rescue capsule with an oxygen tank can be added to each beacon. So, you can wait

for help in a safe area. The principle of spatial navigation on the Moon is illustrated in Figure 9;

*Figure 9. The principle of spatial navigation on the Moon.
Graphic illustration: Egor A. Orlov.*

- The Moon is silent. Unlike Earth, where sound waves can propagate and reflect off surfaces, the lack of atmosphere on the Moon means that there is no environment. We should propose a space capable of manipulating light and color. For example, we could use mobile lighting devices and create functional color environments. A visual show or a color-light oasis is something we can achieve. Many colorful objects fluctuate in shape. Large beamer projects images and movies into the sky. What if we chose the color of the sky as the cover on desktop Windows? It's time for us to learn how to communicate with color! Share color-coded messages, memories, and dreams. Or perhaps the city could be a large art installation, visible from Earth and beyond. We need to become

associative synesthetes. Discuss building drawings using a palette of colors. Adjust the city to a particular color based on your mood or desire. If you are overloaded or under stress, the city receiver works in the background and displays a gray flashing screen. If you are, on the contrary, fully rested and have a plan of action, you may experience white or yellow. We build emotion. A new relationship between color, light, and space. The principle is illustrated in Figure 10;

Figure 10. Color-light oasis. Graphic illustration: Irina S. Kozlova.

- Space debris is abundant in Earth's orbit. It has various shapes and sizes. We must adapt it for utilization in a moon city. For example, debris may be used in new facade solutions. The architectural walls become a multidimensional constructor, losing their monolithic property. Architects should create puzzle-like shapes and fragmental surfaces. The city becomes a blender. It is a useful device to work with different physical products. A bricolage, or patchwork of elements, is created from nearby materials. Can we invent a calculator to synchronize the moon city? A fragment of the facade is illustrated in Figure 11;

Figure 11. Structural facade pattern from debris. Graphic illustration: Irina S. Kozlova.

In summary, the authors conclude that humans were not originally adapted to colonize space due to vulnerability. To achieve this goal, one must wear a bulky spacesuit occupied by multiple life support systems. It's not a cowboy adventure, but rather a highly-technological and secure prison of the body. Therefore, the city of the future should become a new superorganism that aims to provide humans with unlimited powers and the ability to fully exist in space.

The Moon is a great challenge. The lunar environment is extremely dangerous and aggressive. And usual architecture is not applicable in that place. Nonetheless, the Moon can play a crucial role in the advancement of future architecture.

Hypothesis

Today, Earth's architecture is in a state of stagnation. Limited land, zoning rules, infrastructure restrictions, and environmental agendas force mankind to colonize space.

Architecture should break free from the crisis of conventional horizontal-vertical forms and liberate architecture from its terrestrial confines. In 1883 Konstantin Tsiolkovsky wrote the book "Free space" where he showed his ideas about the first spaceship. He made the indisputable claim that "Observable bodies placed in space are naturally called free. This environment may theoretically have no borders, in this case I will call it unlimited" (pp. 9) [14]. This concept gives rise to the notion of unlimited architecture. The design in the extreme conditions of the lunar environment becomes not only a challenge but also a great opportunity. The result of this could be a radical new architecture of the future.

Results

The Moon's Dungeon City is a new concept of space colonization. It gradually reshapes the lunar space. This architectural parasite enters the celestial body and becomes its duplicate. The city can evolve and eventually become a planet. The authors propose an architectural and spatial catalog of principles for its design.

1) Fractality

The fractality operates on the idea of replication. All parts can be duplicated without altering the initial configuration. It allows for the tactical evolution of the architectural composition. The lunar base can adapt to the lunar terrain features by using a fractal structure. Multiplication of cells creates a geometrical pattern, enabling the architecture to be flexible in the inhospitable lunar environment. Moreover, the fractal is capable of self-similarity. This could be the foundation for building a lunar base. The moon city is made up of fragments that have the structural ability to replicate when the scale changes. A copy-paste system unlocks the mathematical potential of the city. We can draw insights from algorithmic design tools, often seen in gaming, to explore the challenges of formgiving.

Modulators will trace forms backwards to their origin and forwards through endless iterations and unexpected outcomes [12]. Fractality generates complex and multilayered models that can be expanded or condensed while maintaining the same level of detail. This allows for exploration of both the microcosm and macrocosm of the city.

2) Modularity

The modularity allows for the creation of continuously evolving architectural forms. The collection of spatial compositions can be assembled depending on given conditions. The structure is easily modified and transformed by breaking it into modular cells. The moonbase's modularity permits adaptation to the lunar environment, as each element operates autonomously. Modules can be combined to form a diverse layout for the lunar base, offering inhabitants multiple route options. Thus, the city evolves into a dynamic landscape of interconnected movements. In addition, the atomization of the system allows for a detailed examination of components such as vectors and nodes. The city can be edited and configured using a grid. This multitool allows an architectural wizard to cast a new world. By experimenting with various configurations and layouts, we can create a multidimensional and unique lunar city.

3) Connectivity

The connectivity allows us to mix everything. Different pieces of the lunar base will be integrated into a spatial network. The development mode can be chosen: structure or chaos. For example, incorporating a central element into a city can create an attractive point for residents. On one hand, such a solution encourages social interaction. On the other hand, the system may collapse due to overload. Residents move to the center and crowd the space during emergencies. This factor makes it safer to adopt a non-centralized architecture. A

decentralized structure provides for convenient movement, resource distribution, and communication between the different parts of the lunar base.

4) Multifunctionality

The multifunctionality makes it possible to create a hybrid urban context on the lunar base. Different spaces can perform multiple functions simultaneously, allowing architects to maximize space utilization. For instance, they expand the available area or create rush hour scenarios. We can create a Hyperbuilding. It mixes interior and exterior, small-scale and large-scale elements, nothingness and the universe. This "extramess" structure will serve as the catalyst of urbanization. The structure may adapt to changes without losing effectiveness. Another feature of the Hyperbuilding is its colossal trajectories. In this situation, we are dealing with an architectural infinite, where the possibility of clear functional zoning is lost. Within this endless landscape, every point in space feels identical, and movement in any direction becomes indistinguishable. Moreover, all the elements of this space are in the same place and equally distant from each other. In addition, the idea of movement becomes lost in Hyperbuilding - it's unclear if one is moving or not. This situation is comparable to a carpet: in the distance we see its exceptional shape and image, but when approaching it we encounter an infinite geometric pattern that disintegrates into chaotic elements. In such an infinite multifunctional object, any point in space can be assigned a function as needed. Each element of the city has the ability to acquire any function and become anything. For example, a home can turn into a spaceship, then a mechanical rover or refrigerator. In the evening, a microwave might work in the cafeteria and then serve as a vacuum cleaner. The city is filled with functions. It is a multifunctional chameleon.

5) Scalability

The scalability may adjust, expand, or reduce the city. When the system expands, it becomes viable to construct multi-level structures and additional functional areas. When reduced, it allows for the creation of mobile zero modules or restoration of the configuration to its original state. Scalability not only enables expansion architecture but also defines the development of a mobile city.

Discussion

We must evolve to master the Moon. Shift our perspective on the world.

In the 17th century, Domingo Gonsalez discovered geese migrating not to southern countries, but directly to the Moon. He constructed a device that lifted him up into the heavens, where encountered a developed culture of lunar inhabitants. This story was written by English bishop Francis Goodwin in "The Man in the Moone" (1638) [4]. He was a believer in the Copernican heliocentric system and the latest theories in magnetism and astronomy.

Later, artist Agnes Meyer-Brandis was interested in this idea. Her works combine scientific facts, imaginary realities, and ancient mythologies. For the project called "The Moon Goose Analogue: Lunar Migration Bird Facility" (2011), she built a star town in the art residence of Pollinaria (Italy) [10]. Here she trained a flock of young geese-astronauts for lunar flight. Agnes bestowed upon them the names of renowned astronauts. Their life began with seeing a person dressed in a spacesuit. A specially equipped farm taught the geese how to fly behind a luminous ball, walk on the moonscape, eat special lunar dandelions and send messages to the Earth using the Morse code. As their surrogate mother, Agnes had to spend the weeks following the hatching in close contact with the eleven geese. According to schedule, the birds will go on their first unmanned flight to the satellite in 2027.

This experiment reveals that we have a lot of work to do before we can explore space. The goal is not just to create a new architecture. The first step is to imagine a lunar person. What message does architecture have to communicate to space?

Lunar space is the ideal platform for the most futuristic architectural solutions. The inhospitable relief of the Moon necessitates a three-dimensional design. In space, traditional ideas about cities are giving way to constantly transforming and mobile structures. We must consider and avoid the shortcomings of Earth-based design, as the universe offers an opportunity to develop urban concepts on a multi-planetary scale.

References

[1] Banham, R. (2020). *Megastructure. Urban futures of the recent past*. The Monacelli Press.

[2] Bratton, B. (2020). *The Terraforming*. Strelka Press Publ.

[3] Brennan, L., Siecinski, R., Tremayne, M., Patel, A., Patel, P., Singh, S., Basily, B., & Benaroya, H. (2023). Mechanical design of a lunar habitat structure and deployment mechanism. *Acta Astronautica*, 213(December), 102-120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2023.09.001>

[4] Goodwin, F. (2013). *The Man in the Moone*. Firestone Books.

[5] Haeuplik-Meusburger, S., & Bannova, O. (2023). Reflections on early lunar base design: From sketch to the first moon landing. *Acta Astronautica*, 202(January), 729-741. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2022.09.021>

[6] Harrison, A.A. (2010). Humanizing outer space: Architecture, habitability, and behavioral health. *Acta*

Astronautica, 66(5–6), 890-896.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2009.09.008>

[7] Heinlein, R.A. (1997). *The Moon is a Harsh Mistress*. First Edition. Orb Books.

[8] Lai, J (2021, June). *Spaceship Hour*. e-flux Architecture. Retrieved October 21, 2024, from <https://www.e-flux.com/architecture/cascades/405781/spaceship-hour>

[9] Meuser, P. (2022). *Galina Balashova: Architect of the Soviet Space Programme* (Bilingual edition). DOM Publishers.

[10] Meyer-Brandis, A. (2012). *The Moon Goose Analogue: Lunar Migration Bird Facility*. [Video]. Vimeo. <https://vimeo.com/38986659>

[11] Sarkis, H., Barrio, R.S., & Kozlowski, G. (2019). *The World as an Architectural Project*. The Massachusetts Institute of Technology Press.

[12] The Why Factory. Maas, W., Madrazo, F., & Hulsman, B. (2018). *Copy Paste: Bad Ass Copy Guide*. nai010 publisher.

[13] Tol, A.L., Lipinska, M.B., Foing, B., & Greenwood-George, E. (2022). Sky lake: Moon environment design. *Acta Astronautica*, 201(December), 554-563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2022.07.056>

[14] Tsiolkovsky, K (1989). *Promyshlennoe osvoenie kosmosa* [Industrial space exploration]. Mashinostroenie Publ.

[15] Zefel'd, V.V. (2011). The object-spatial environment of the spacecraft cabin. *National Journal of Psychology*, 1, 93-99. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/predmetno-ppoctpanctvennoe-okruzhenie-kabiny-kosmicheskogo-korablya/viewer>

[16] Wang, Q., Feng, P., Jansen, K., & Bao, C. (2024). A novel rigidizable inflatable lunar habitation system: Design concept and material characterization. *Materials & Design*, 246(113289). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2024.113289>

[17] Young, L (2021, August). *Planet City: A sci-fi vision of an astonishing regenerative future* [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/AX4ewS-YIbA?si=rRc1BLMGCTEgCzDx>

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